

Data management plan

D.1.1

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1. About the deliverable

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is an official project deliverable (D1) with its initial version (D1.1) due in month 6 (March 2025). This DMP will be in development throughout the project and will describe the datasets produced through the NiD4OCEAN project. Open data will be available at NiD4OCEAN's community on Zenodo available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/nid4ocean>. Data are expected to be produced starting from M5, with regular updates until M34.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be reviewed and updated regularly with input from all partners involved in D1. A final version will be released in the last year of the project, using [Argos DMP](#) with the built-in Horizon Europe template to ensure compliance with FAIR principles and Open Science requirements.

Argos DMP is an online tool that helps create, manage, and share Data Management Plans in line with funding guidelines and best practices.

The current version of the DMP describes the implementation of Open Access, and data management principles in the NiD4OCEAN's project. In addition, the DMP will outline the access rights of consortium participants to data held by other consortium members in accordance to jointly agreed rules (Consortium agreement).

NiD4OCEAN complies to the principles of Open Science according to the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement (MGA - version 1.2) current available via URL https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/agr-contr/general-mga_horizon-euratom_en.pdf.

2. List of acronyms abbreviations, and definitions

DMP	Data Management Plan
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
M	Month
Green open Access	Self-archiving (green open access) means that a published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived (deposited) in an online repository before, alongside or after its publication. In some cases, the author can choose to delay access to the article (embargo period).
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NBS	Nature-based solution
NiDs	Nature-inclusive designs
WP	Work package

3. Introduction

NiD4OCEAN will advance the emerging field of nature-inclusive designs, NiDs, (and nature-based solutions, NBS, in general) for offshore renewables by providing effective, novel, context-dependent solutions to industry, managers, and policymakers. An Innovation Challenge Series will be developed to promote novel NiDs and NBS for each ecoregion's wind and floating solar structures (addressing issues such as design, material choice, noise, and laying cables). Each ecoregion will use a transdisciplinary approach to develop context-dependent metrics and impact assessment frameworks to evaluate the benefits and risks of selected NiDs for offshore wind. Moreover, data and monitoring requirements for evaluating the performance of NiDs will be identified to be later incorporated into recommendations towards standards. An evidence-based decision-support tool

will be co-created with industry and managers to provide clarity on the selection process of NiDs in offshore wind farms. Finally, a co-created policy toolkit for the requirements of offshore wind development to comply with biodiversity protection and restoration targets will be delivered. NiD4OCEAN strives to raise awareness across stakeholders on the need to prioritize win-win solutions for biodiversity and decarbonization.

NiD4OCEAN follows the EC's Open Science policy, and applies the FAIR principles to all project outputs, as well as to the collected primary data as described in the DMP. As stated in DG Research & Innovation's study on Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property Rights (2022)¹, the principle of “as open as possible and as closed as necessary” must be understood in the sense that *“OS categorically does not mean indiscriminate openness, but the default rule is that any reason for making it closed should be made evident and that the limits based on the nature of the information already serve as a reasonable scenario.”* (p. 8, Open Science and IPR. How can they better interact? Report of Study, 2022). Whereas articles have established best practices for balancing IPR and OA, research data have some different nuances to consider as data or facts alone do not have IP protection such as copyright, however databases do. In order to employ the ability to make datasets inter-operable and available for re-use, the IPR strategy must ensure that proper consents are in place.

¹ Available at: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/publications/all-publications/open-science-and-intellectual-property-rights_en

4. Data summary

4.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project

The primary goal of data generation and re-use in NiD4OCEAN is to assess the ecological and operational impact of NiDs in offshore wind and floating solar environments. The collected and re-used data will contribute to impact assessments, policy recommendations, and decision-support tools.

4.2 Use of existing data

The project may re-use existing datasets where relevant to establish baselines and enhance the analysis of nature-inclusive designs (NiDs). Any re-used data will be appropriately cited to acknowledge the original sources.

4.3 Expected data size

The exact size of the data to be generated or re-used is not yet determined. However, the size of each dataset will be specified once available and documented accordingly in the DMP

4.4 Data origin/provenance

A high-level summary of the currently expected datasets from the different WPs are summarized in Table 1. This list will be updated during the lifetime of this DMP, and it might be subdivided into datasets from specific deliverables. For this initial version it is indicative of important datasets to be produced.

4.5 Data utility

The data may be useful for scientists, industry, policy makers and society.

5.1 Summary of Table 1:

Dataset Name: Dataset identifier

Dataset Type: Type/category of data

Expected Data Type: File formats and structure

Deliverable: Milestone or output associated with the dataset

Partner Responsible: Responsible partner for managing the dataset

Expected Delivery Date: Expected Delivery in project months (M)

Dissemination Level: Visibility and access level of the dataset

- **Public:** Intended for open access by the general public. These datasets will be uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring long-term availability. Access may be subject to an embargo period, depending on the timing of related scientific publications.
- **Restricted:** Access is limited due to confidentiality agreements, ethical considerations, or legal constraints. These datasets are available only to designated partners.

GDPR: Contain personal or sensitive information, complying with data protection laws, including GDPR requirements for consent, anonymization, and security.

- **N/A:** Does not contain personal or sensitive information
- **Yes:** dataset complies with GDPR standards for privacy and protection of personal data.

Table 1 – Overview of expected datasets

Dataset name	Dataset description	Dataset type	Expected data format	Deliverable	Partner responsible	Expected delivery	Dissemination level	GDPR Compliant?
Overview NiDs	Overview of all our NiDs	Categorical	Recommended: .csv Acceptable: .xls/.xlsx/.mdb/.accdb/.dbf/.ods	D2.1	Noordzee	M5	Public	N/A
Policy relevant species dataset	final list of policy-relevant species, organized by study zone (one sheet per zone). It includes species names, conservation status and their traits sensitive to OWF impacts and NID measures.	Categorical	Recommended: .csv Acceptable: .xls/.xlsx/.mdb/.accdb/.dbf/.ods	D2.2	ICM-CSIC	M24	Public	N/A
Policy relevant habitat dataset	final list of policy-relevant habitats and communities, organized by study zone (one sheet per zone). It includes species names, conservation status and their traits sensitive to OWF impacts	Categorical	Recommended: .csv Acceptable: .xls/.xlsx/.mdb/.accdb/.dbf/.ods	D2.2	ICM-CSIC	M24	Public	N/A

	and NID measures.							
Policy relevant species and habitat selection framework	Outlines the framework for selecting policy-relevant species and habitats based on their conservation status, presence in the study zone, and sensitivity to OWF, NIDs and mitigation measures. It details the steps to identify and prioritize species and habitats and ensures a standardized species and habitat selection process across the three study zones.	Categorical	Recommended: .rtf./ .pdf / .odt Acceptable: .doc/ .docx	D2.2	ICM-CSIC	M24	Public	N/A
Validation of preliminary results (reference points for social sustainability and equity) at the Baltic context workshop - Milestone 10	Document with key messages obtained from the workshop event, following GDPR rules and considering anonymity and confidentiality issues	Text	Recommended: .rtf./ .pdf / .odt Acceptable: .doc/ .docx	D2.4	NIVA-DK	M12	Restricted	Yes

Validation of preliminary results (reference points for social sustainability and equity) at the North Sea context workshop - Milestone 10	Document with key messages obtained from the workshop event, following GDPR rules and considering anonymity and confidentiality issues	Text	Recommended: .rtf/.pdf/.odt Acceptable: .doc/.docx	D2.4	NIVA-DK	M12	Restricted	Yes
Validation of preliminary results (reference points for social sustainability and equity) at the West Med context workshop - Milestone 10	Document with key messages obtained from the workshop event, following GDPR rules and considering anonymity and confidentiality issues	Text	Recommended: .rtf/.pdf/.odt Acceptable: .doc/.docx	D2.4	NIVA-DK	M12	Restricted	Yes
Gap analysis		Text	Recommended: .rtf/.pdf/.odt Acceptable: .doc/.docx	D3.1	Wageningen University & Research (WUR)	M18	Public	N/A
Open Challenge report	Report of the different projects presented to the Open Challenge for SMEs.	Text	Recommended: .rtf/.pdf/.odt Acceptable: .doc/.docx	D3.2	NIVA-NO	M27	Restricted	N/A
University Challenges report	Summary report of the different projects presented to the	Text	Recommended: .rtf/.pdf/.odt Acceptable: .doc/.docx	D3.2	NIVA-NO	M27	Restricted	N/A

	University Innovation Challenges.							
Tested NiD assessment report	Output of the hydrodynamic behavior of the tested NiD at the Deltares facilities	Experimental Data	Recommended: .csv Acceptable: .xls/.xlsx/.mdb/.accdb .dbf/.ods	D3.3	Deltares	M34	Restricted	N/A
Off-shore wind standards	Summary of existing offshore wind standards and will be used to identify opportunities for NiDs integration	Text	Recommended: .rtf./pdf/.odt Acceptable: .doc/.docx	D5.2	DNV	M19	Public	N/A
Model output	Model output reflecting the relative change in species occurrence and overall biodiversity in response to offshore wind and NiDs in selected case study areas.	Other	Recommended: .csv Acceptable: .xls/.xlsx/.mdb/.accdb .dbf/.ods	D4.3	National Institute of Aquatic Resources (DTU)	M36	Public	N/A
Dataset of modeling tools for impact assessment of NiDs for OWF	List of modelling tools for assessment of NiD impacts and their TRL levels identified for	Categorical	Recommended: .csv Acceptable: .xls/.xlsx/.mdb/.accdb .dbf/.ods	D4.1	Deltares	M18	Public	N/A

	selected case study areas							
Model output	Model output reflecting the impact of specific example NID on local region	Other	Other	D4.2	Akvaplan-NIVA	M30	Public	N/A

5. FAIR data

5.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Primary data and metadata will be handled according to recognised standards for sampling/collection, laboratory work and analysis, until publication and dissemination. For open research data Zenodo [3] will be used.

5.2 Persistent and unique identifiers

Many of the data repositories under consideration supports unique identifiers and focus for publication data will be on repositories that supports DOI generation. During project execution the use of unique identifiers is good way to ensure traceability of shared data.

5.3 Naming conventions

The following naming convention will be used in the project, following accepted discipline standards.

For results and media and quantitative data files:

[Task code (without dots)]_[arbitrary semantic identifier]_[data status tag].[file extension]

Below is an example of file naming for a fully quality assured result dataset stored in an excel file (.xlsx), produced as part of T2.1 and concerning the list of existing NiDs to be incorporated into the Toolbox:

T11_nid_mapping_list_F.csv

Note the use of “underscore” to avoid spaces between characters in the file name.

The data status tag refers to the level of quality assurance of data included in the file. Two tag options are possible:

F = Final, fully quality assured results (e.g. data)

IP = Data where quality assurance is still in progress

For files of popular or scientific dissemination papers:

[Task code (without dots)]_[Author1]_[year]_[dissemination type].[file extension]

Below is an example of file naming for a reprint of a scientific paper in .pdf format, produced as part of Task T2.2 produced by Danyus and colleagues in 2026:

T21_Danyus_2026_SCI.pdf

The dissemination type tag refers to the type of dissemination. Two tag options are possible:

SCI = Scientific publication in a technical (e.g. peer reviewed) journal

POP = Popular dissemination (including dissemination oriented to stakeholders, policy makers and the general public)

If based on those criteria more than one file share the same name an alphabetical tag will be included after the year, e.g.:

T21_Danyus_2026b_SCI.pdf

Versioning

The need for versioning will depend on the data, data owner and need for data preservation. Zenodo is the chosen tool to ensure long-term preservation.

5.5 Making data openly accessible

The data repository Zenodo, clustered with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will be used to archive research data, other more specific repositories can be considered. Self-archiving or so-called 'green' Open Access will be applied through development of an internal repository. This will be based on needs by consortium members and stakeholders.

5.6 Interoperability

To make publication data interoperable NiD4OCEAN will focus on using accessible and broadly accepted formats, for example, through providing tabular data in CSV format with standardized encoding.

5.7 Re-use of data (licensing)

NiD4Ocean's recommendation is to attach a Commons Licences (CC BY or CC0) to deposited publication data to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and especially disseminate our results.

6. Other research outputs

Beyond datasets, this project might produce a variety of research outputs, including software scripts, protocols, and methodologies. Any custom code developed during the project will be shared through open repositories like GitHub and archived in Zenodo with a suitable open-source license (e.g., MIT, GPL). Publications resulting from the project will be deposited in Zenodo in line with Horizon Europe's Open Science guidelines.

7. Allocation of Resources

We have allocated specific resources to ensure proper data management throughout the project. This includes budget provisions for data storage, processing, and open-access publishing fees. Long-term data preservation will be covered under the project's Open Science budget. The project provides secure storage infrastructure, and dedicated data manager, along with dataset responsible that will oversee compliance with FAIR principles and DMP implementation. If additional costs arise, we will explore institutional support or relevant funding mechanisms.

8. Data security

All project data will be stored on secure institutional servers with controlled access. If any sensitive or personal data is generated, it will be encrypted and handled in full compliance with GDPR and institutional policies. Access will be restricted to authorized team members, with authentication and logging measures in place to ensure security. Regular backups will be maintained in multiple locations to prevent data loss. If cloud storage is used, it will be limited to providers that fully comply with EU data protection regulations.

9. Ethical principles under Horizon Europe

Please refer to document [Ethics & IPR strategy](#).

10. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) under Horizon Europe

Please refer to document [Ethics & IPR strategy](#).

11. Other issues

At this stage, we do not anticipate any legal, ethical, or technical issues affecting data management. However, should any challenges arise, we will address them in consultation with institutional and

funding body representatives. The DMP will be treated as a living document, updated as needed to reflect any changes in project scope, new policies, or unforeseen developments.

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